

A Study of Family Climate of Male and Female B.Ed. Teacher-Trainees of Bareilly District

Ms. Baby Zoofishan¹, Dr. Pratibha Sagar²

¹Research Scholar, Department of B.Ed./M.Ed., Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences, M.J.P. Rohilkh and University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh.

²Assistant Professor, Department of B.Ed./M.Ed., Faculty of Education and Allied Sciences, M.J.P. Rohilkh and University, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.55248/gengpi.2022.3.11.11>

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to find out the difference of different dimensions of family climate of B.Ed. teacher-trainees in relation to their gender. Descriptive survey method was used for this study. A sample of 160 B.Ed. teacher-trainees was selected by using random sampling technique from four B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district. Family Climate Scale developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019) used for data collection. Data was analyzed using Mean, S.D. and t-test. Finding reveals that significant difference has been found in acceptance, independence and control dimensions of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Keywords: Family Climate, B.Ed. Teacher-Trainees, Gender.

Introduction:

The family is the most significant factor in a child's upbringing and personality development. It serves as the starting point for personality development. The impact of the family environment on a child's development is greater than that of any other environmental component. Psychologists, sociologists, and educators opined that the family has the greatest impact on a child's development. The word climate is more comprehensive one which includes within itself the word environment. The human elements surrounding the child constitute the environment. It embraces the social, physical and emotional activities of the family. All these combined together constitute the family climate. The family climate has a significant impact on how children behave as they grow up. Family is the first social climate where individual fulfils his/her physical, mental and cultural needs. Family interaction plays an important role in the development of an individual. Thus we can say that family climate moulds the behaviour, personality, attitude, aptitude, self-esteem and mental health of an individual (Kaur *et al*, 2015).

Family climate plays an important role in every field of student's life. In this specific context the present research will undertaken to specifically provide empirical answers of these questions like what is difference of different dimensions of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. To conduct this study, researcher has used **Family Climate Scale** developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019). This scale comprises of 69 items within three main dimensions. (I) **Relationship Dimensions**, (II) **Personal Growth Dimensions**, (III) **System Maintenance Dimensions**.

(I) **Relationship Dimensions** --- It divided into four sub-dimensions.

1. **Cohesion** – Degree of commitment, help, and support family members provide for one another.
2. **Expressiveness** – Extent to which family members are encouraged to act openly and express their feelings and thoughts directly.
3. **Conflict** – Amount of openly expressed aggression and conflict among family members.
4. **Acceptance and Caring** – Extent to which the members are unconditionally accepted and the degree to which caring is expressed in the family.

(II) **Personal Growth Dimensions** -- It divided into two sub-dimensions.

1. **Independence** – Extent to which family members are assertive and independently make their own decisions.
2. **Active Recreational Orientation** – Extent of participation in social and recreational activities.

(III) **System Maintenance Dimensions** -- It divided into two sub-dimensions

1. **Organization** – Degree of importance of clear organization structure in planning family activities and responsibilities.
2. **Control** – Degree of limit setting within a family.

Review of Related Literature

Robert &Kadhiravan (2019) investigated the influence of family climate on emotional intelligence of higher secondary students. A sample of 240 higher secondary students was selected from Dharampuri district, Tamilnadu. A significant influence of family environment was found on emotional intelligence of students. Significant difference was showed on emotional intelligence of male and female students and arts & science stream students.**Kumar and Lal (2014)** healthy family environment found to have higher academic achievement in compare to children belonging to unhealthy family environment. **Chawla (2012)** found positive relationship between family environment and academic achievement. **Mishra and Bamba (2012)** found contribution of family climate on academic achievement of a child. Review of related literature reveals that various studies had been conducted family climate and other variables such as mental health, academic achievement, anxiety, life-satisfaction, occupational aspiration, intelligence, adjustment, adolescent-period etc. But it was found that no study has been conducted of different dimensions of family climate of B.Ed. teacher trainees in relation to gender. Hence the researcher has decided to undertake, the study of family climate of B.Ed. teacher trainees in relation to gender.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To explore gender difference in the cohesionaspect of family climate of B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. To study the expressiveness aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
3. To find out the conflict aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
4. To investigate the acceptance aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
5. To search the independence aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
6. To detect the recreational aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
7. To study the organization aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
8. To find out the control aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant difference of cohesion aspect of family climateof male and femaleB.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. There is no significant difference of expressiveness aspectof family climateof male and femaleB.Ed. teacher-trainees.
3. There is no significant difference of conflict aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
4. There is no significant difference of acceptance aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
5. There is no significant difference of independence aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
6. There is no significant difference of recreational aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
7. There is no significant difference of organization aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
8. There is no significant difference of control aspect of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Research Design & Methodology:

The researcher used Descriptive Survey method. Population of the present study consists of all the teacher-trainees of B.Ed. colleges affiliated to M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly. A Sample of 160 teacher-trainees of four B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district was selected with the help of simple random sampling techniques. **Family Climate Scale (FCS)** developed by HarpreetBhatia &N.K.Chadha(2019) was used for the study. Data were analysed using Mean, S.D., and t-test.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference of cohesion dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-1: result of t-test of cohesion dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	50.52	6.701	0.375	not significant
Female	116	50.96	6.110		

The above table shows that the t-value is 0.375 that is not significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. Thus there no significant difference of cohesion dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. Sonull hypothesis is accepted. So, we can say that both genders are equally cohesive.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference of expressiveness dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-2: result of t-test of expressiveness dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	30.09	3.833	1.122	not significant
Female	116	30.97	4.652		

The above table shows that the t-value is 1.122 that is not significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. Thus there no significant difference of expressiveness dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. So null hypothesis is accepted. It can be concluded that both male and female teacher trainees are equally expressive.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference of conflict dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-3: result of t-test of conflict dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	40.43	4.592	1.544	not significant
Female	116	41.79	5.881		

The above table shows that the t-value is 1.544 that is not significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. Thus there no significant difference of conflict dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. So our null hypothesis is accepted. It can be seen that no conflict issues are there with male and female teacher trainees in their families.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference of acceptance dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-4: result of t-test of acceptance dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	42.27	4.990	2.097*	significant
Female	116	44.16	5.353		

*= significant at 0.05 significance level

The above table shows that the t-value is 2.097 that is significant at 0.05 level. Thus there is significant difference of acceptance dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. So our null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Mean score of female is greater than their counterparts. So acceptance of females is higher.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant difference of independence dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-5: result of t-test of independence dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	29.20	3.714	2.637**	significant
Female	116	31.06	4.592		

**= significant at 0.01 significance level

The above table shows that the t-value is 2.637 that is significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. Thus there is significant difference of independence dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. So our null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Mean score of females shows higher independence as compared to male.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant difference of recreational dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-6: result of t-test of recreational dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	28.30	3.561	1.385	not significant
Female	116	29.21	4.100		

The above table shows that the t-value is 1.385 that is not significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. Thus there no significant difference of recreational dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. So our null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 7: There is no significant difference of organization dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-7: result of t-test of organization dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	7.41	1.647	1.519	not significant
Female	116	7.85	1.664		

The above table shows that the t-value is 1.519 that is not significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. Thus there no significant difference of organization dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. So our null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 8: There is no significant difference of control dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-8: result of t-test of control dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Result
Male	44	13.82	2.423	1.977*	significant
Female	116	14.70	2.908		

*= significant at 0.05 significance level

The above table shows that the t-value is 1.977 that is significant at 0.05 level. Thus there no significant difference of control dimension of family climate of male and female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. So our null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the result revealed that boys and girls had better quality of family environment on different aspects like expressiveness, conflict and caring, active recreational orientation. Whereas, girls scored high on acceptance, independence and control aspects of family environment as compare to boys as they were found less organized and had less control of family on them.

REFERENCES

- Chawla, N. A. (2012). The relationship between family environment and academic achievement. *Indian Spream Research Journal*,1(2).
- Deka, R.S. (2018). *Family environment, emotional intelligence and aggression among juvenile delinquents* (Ph.D. Thesis). University of Gauhati.
- Doley, L. (2018). The impact of home environment factors on academic achievement of adolescents. *Research World Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce*, 9(1), 137-147.
- Jain, K. &Mohta, S. (2019). The impact of home environmenton academic achievement of secondary school students. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 3(4), 808-811.
- Kaur, M., Dhillon, S. S. & Kaur, K. (2015). A study of relationship of family environment with mental health of adolescent of Sirsa district. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(19), 472-475.
- Kumar, R. &Lal, R. (2014). A study of academic achievement in relation to family environment among adolescent. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 2(1), 146-155.
- Mishra, S. &Bamba ,V. (2012). Impact of family environment on academic achievement of secondary school students in science subject. *International Journal of Research in Economic and Social Sciences*, 2(5).
- Robert, J. &Kadhiravan, S.(2019). Influence of family environment on emotional intelligence among youth. *International Journal of Science & Technology Research*, 8(11), 3664-3670.